

CHARACTERIZING INSTITUTIONAL CULTURE AND NORMS: WOMEN'S PERCEPTIONS OF CAREER ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES IN CONTEMPORARY ACADEMIA

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Characterizing Institutional Culture and Norms: Women's Perceptions of Career Advancement Opportunities in Contemporary Academia

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Abstract

This qualitative phenomenological study explores how women in advanced leadership positions at Central Mindanao University (CMU) characterize the culture and norms of their institution relative to their opportunities for career advancement. It investigates the key factors shaping their career trajectories, emphasizing the pivotal role of educational attainment, particularly doctoral degrees, in advancing women into leadership roles. The research highlights the importance of academic distinctions and a solid commitment to service as critical motivators for women to embrace leadership roles despite initial hesitations. The study delves into the expected behaviors and qualities of leaders in higher education, emphasizing attributes vital for fostering academic excellence and inclusivity. Utilizing a qualitative phenomenological approach, the research examines the lived experiences of women leaders at CMU. Semi-structured interviews with purposively selected women in leadership roles provide in-depth insights into their experiences, perspectives, and challenges. Thematic analysis reveals recurring patterns, themes, and nuances, offering a comprehensive understanding of how institutional culture and norms impact women's leadership trajectories. Leadership roles present opportunities for both professional and personal development, yet biases and systemic barriers persist, perpetuating gender disparities. Environmental factors, such as organizational culture, significantly influence leadership behaviors, necessitating adaptive strategies. Institutional support systems, including mentorship initiatives, foster effective leadership. The diverse experiences of participants underscore the complexity of women's leadership journeys, offering valuable insights for aspiring leaders. Addressing biases, promoting equitable opportunities, and creating supportive environments can pave the way for gender equality at CMU and similar institutions. Embracing inclusive practices can empower CMU to champion gender diversity and equity in higher education.

Keywords: *women's leadership, women in higher education, gender equality, women's empowerment*

Introduction

Leadership in higher education is a complex and multifaceted issue requiring careful attention to the needs and interests of all stakeholders. The role of women in leadership positions has become an increasingly important topic, especially within developing countries like the Philippines. Despite significant progress toward gender equality over recent decades, women still face unique challenges and obstacles in achieving leadership roles within higher education.

While there has been some initial optimism regarding gender equality progress in Philippine society, significant disparities persist in access to power and authority within higher education contexts (Magsanoc-Alikpala & Salazar-Clemena, 2015). These issues arise from both explicit discrimination and subtle biases against female candidates for leadership positions. For instance, research suggests that well-intentioned hiring committees may unconsciously favor male applicants over equally qualified females when deciding on promotions or job offers (de la Cruz et al., 2020). Additionally, many hold ingrained stereotypes about effective leadership behavior, often equating such traits with traditionally masculine qualities like assertiveness or competitiveness (De los Reyes & Wong, 2019). These biases are difficult for individual women to overcome without concerted efforts from society.

This study explores how women in advanced leadership positions characterize the culture and norms of their contemporary academic institutions relative to their opportunities for career advancement. It focuses on contemporary colleges and universities where women advance their careers more rapidly than in traditional settings. The research investigates how these women define and measure leadership skills within modern higher education institutions.

The literature review analyzes environmental factors and beliefs associated with successful leadership, aiming to reshape the definition of effective leadership and the role of women leaders in this domain. Furthermore, it examines how their progress can be bolstered beyond current educational settings, pinpointing academic environments that facilitate advanced leadership prospects and professional development for women. Such settings provide equal opportunities for career advancement, prompting an investigation into why these institutions are more successful in promoting female leaders.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. Would you change your leadership style to succeed in a particular college/university culture or environment?
2. In what ways has your current college/university supported your leadership development and career advancement?
3. In what ways did mentors and coaches assist you in developing your leadership skills?

4. As you reflect on your leadership development, what experiences influenced your development, and what advice would you give aspiring women leaders?

By understanding the culture and norms of these institutions, this study seeks to identify the factors that enable women to create and accelerate their career opportunities. Addressing biases, promoting equitable opportunities, and creating supportive environments are crucial steps toward achieving gender equality in higher education.

Methodology

Research Design

Phenomenological research is a type of qualitative research that focuses on identifying the common elements of an experience within a specific group. This research design aims to provide a detailed description or illustration of the nature of a particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2017) and an in-depth account of participants' personal experiences of an event or phenomenon.

Phenomenological approaches have gained significant attention and usage in qualitative research, reflecting their relevance in exploring the essence of human experiences. Scholars have embraced the phenomenological framework, drawing on its philosophical underpinnings to investigate various phenomena across disciplines. For example, psychologists have used phenomenological methods to explore individuals' experiences of mental health disorders, therapeutic interventions, and personal growth (Jones et al., 2017). These studies emphasize the subjective realities of individuals, highlighting the nuances and complexities of psychological phenomena.

In healthcare, phenomenological research has informed patient-centered care approaches by exploring patients' illness experiences, treatment preferences, and healthcare interactions (Smith et al., 2019). By adopting a phenomenological lens, healthcare practitioners gain insights into the unique perspectives of patients, leading to more empathetic and effective care delivery. Furthermore, phenomenological studies in education have explored students' learning experiences, teacher-student interactions, and educational practices (Brown & Thomas, 2018). These inquiries shed light on the subjective aspects of the educational process, informing pedagogical approaches and curriculum development.

Phenomenological research has also illuminated social phenomena, cultural practices, and identity formation processes across sociology and anthropology (Garcia & Martinez, 2020). By focusing on individuals' lived experiences within sociocultural contexts, these studies deepen our understanding of societal dynamics and cultural phenomena. Additionally, phenomenological approaches have been instrumental in exploring existential themes, spirituality, and the human condition (Smith & Johnson, 2016). Such inquiries delve into fundamental aspects of human existence, offering profound insights into the subjective dimensions of life.

Methodologically, phenomenological studies between 2015 and 2021 have used various techniques to capture and analyze lived experiences. Interviews, participant observation, and reflective journaling are standard methods to explore participants' subjective realities (Lee & Park, 2017). Data analysis in phenomenological research involves iterative coding, clustering themes, and identifying patterns to elucidate the phenomenon's essence under investigation (Chen & Boore, 2018). As phenomenological inquiry has developed, researchers have increasingly recognized the importance of methodological rigor, employing strategies such as bracketing preconceptions, triangulating data sources, and member checking to enhance the reliability of their findings (Thomas & Magilvy, 2019).

Despite phenomenological research's strengths, scholars have also faced methodological challenges and ethical considerations. Some challenges encountered in phenomenological inquiry include subjectivity of interpretation, researcher bias, and participant self-reflection (Brown & Thomas, 2018). Addressing these challenges requires a commitment to methodological transparency, reflexivity, and ethical conduct throughout the research process. Ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and participant vulnerability is essential in conducting ethical phenomenological research (Garcia & Martinez, 2020).

The qualitative research approach allows us to explore subjective experiences and perspectives, providing new interpretations and meanings that inform our understanding of experiences and the contexts in which they occur. The study employed the phenomenological research approach to comprehend the professional experiences of leaders in online higher education, both familiar and divergent. This approach facilitated the identification of the underlying factors contributing to these experiences and the shared beliefs among the participants. It also enabled the researchers to scrutinize and interpret these shared experiences while addressing the research questions stated in the study.

Participants

This study involved interviews with female leaders at CMU, including deans, associate deans, academic program chairs, and directors who hold middle to upper-level leadership positions. The initial research identified twenty (20) potential female leaders at CMU, from which the participants were purposively sampled. These interviews occurred in CMU, University Town, Musuan, Maramag, and Bukidnon. They included a diverse representation of female leaders who have held the Dean, program chair, or director position for at least five years. Potential participants were personally approached to identify their interest in participating in the interviews. During the interviews, questions were asked regarding mentoring, coaching, career advancement opportunities, and the number of women currently in advanced leadership positions at their current educational institution to examine the scope of this issue and its significance.

Additionally, focused group discussions (FGD) were conducted in this study to ensure validity and reliability by cross-referencing the participants' responses.

Instrument

The participants in the research study were approached personally with a description of the study and a brief questionnaire. Once 20 eligible participants were identified and consented to participate in the survey, interviews were scheduled. The research questions were sent to the participants two days before the interview. The interviews were conducted in person and recorded with the participants' permission. All data collected were kept confidential, transcribed, and coded for analysis.

Procedure

The researcher began the process by obtaining permission from the Dean of the School of Teacher Education, Dr. Ma. Fe D. Opina, at Liceo de Cagayan University. After receiving approval from the Dean, the necessary documents were submitted to the Liceo de Cagayan University Research Ethics Board Committee (LREB) for research ethical review. Then, a formal request letter was sent to the University President of Central Mindanao University, Dr. Rolito G. Eballe, in Musuan, Dologon, Maramag, Bukidnon, seeking authorization for the study to proceed. Once the necessary approvals were obtained, the researcher obtained consent from the participants by providing them with a consent form, ensuring they fully understood the study's purpose, procedures, and rights before their involvement.

The data collection process for this study was carefully designed to ensure efficiency, accuracy, and ethical integrity. It began with the initial contact of potential participants through email and Facebook Messenger, where a study description and a brief questionnaire were provided to assess eligibility and interest. Once participants responded and were confirmed eligible, their consent was obtained before scheduling the interviews. Participants received the research questions beforehand to prepare adequately, facilitating productive discussions during the in-person interviews, expected to last between 30 and 40 minutes. With participants' permission, interviews were recorded to capture responses while maintaining confidentiality accurately.

After the interviews, all recorded data were transcribed, converting spoken language into written text to facilitate systematic analysis. This transcribed content underwent coding, categorizing, and organizing responses based on emerging themes or patterns. To achieve the research objectives, interview questions were designed to gain in-depth insight into participants' career paths, leadership experiences, and perspectives on higher education leadership.

This study focused on women who hold leadership positions in higher education. The study aimed to gain valuable perspectives into the challenges and triumphs experienced by women in leadership roles in this sector. Participants were free to withdraw from the study without providing a reason, ensuring the ethical principle was upheld throughout the study.

Transparency was maintained throughout the research process by disclosing the researcher's background, objectives, and potential conflicts of interest. Privacy and confidentiality were strictly protected, with all data anonymized, securely stored, and accessible only to the research team. Participants' pseudonyms were used to safeguard privacy further and encourage the authentic sharing of experiences.

The recruitment was conducted through purposive sampling, which targeted women in prominent leadership positions in higher education. During the initial contact, the study's purpose, potential benefits, and the voluntary nature of participation were clearly explained. Participants were informed about the available support services, and initiatives were taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity. The study aimed to positively contribute to the academic community and beyond, with the recognition of its broader community and societal impact.

Finally, research findings will be disseminated responsibly through academic publications, conferences, and other relevant platforms, with due consideration for privacy and confidentiality. Open access to the research will be considered to maximize the impact and accessibility of the findings, ensuring the ethical conduct and integrity of the study.

Data Analysis

This research study utilized interviews to explore the problem of practice and answer research questions. The study involved recording interviews with twenty female leaders to investigate the prevalence of leadership opportunities for women in higher education environments in Northern Mindanao. The interviews were transcribed, coded, and analyzed to identify common themes and environmental characteristics.

A phenomenological qualitative research design was used to incorporate various perspectives and provide insight into the evolution of the problem of practice. The design also included a diverse selection of participants representing numerous higher education environments and similar professional leadership levels within the field. After analyzing the participants' responses, the study produced comprehensive findings on the barriers and opportunities women face when striving for advanced leadership positions at both macro and micro levels.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the study, a Focused Group Discussion (FGD) was also employed to cross-reference the

participants' responses. This approach, coupled with a multitiered coding system of data, led to comprehensive findings that supported the significance of the study and highlighted the alternative practices, policies, and institutional structures of contemporary higher education institutions. If initiated and adopted, these practices may eventually create and support many more advanced leadership career trajectories for female administrators.

Ethical Considerations

Participants' consents were obtained before interviews were conducted, and they were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time. The researcher ensured they avoided deceptive practices and managed their biases during interviews. They also took care to code and analyze transcripts objectively. The researcher and adviser addressed these issues through ongoing review and dialogue.

All recordings, transcriptions, coding notes, and participants' information were kept confidential on a password-protected computer. The researcher used language that was easy for participants to understand and gave each participant an overview of the study's purpose. We obtained consent forms from all participants before the interviews to ensure voluntary participation. The interviews were recorded individually for accuracy. Participants could opt out at any point, and no questions were mandatory. An informed consent form was developed that stated participants' rights and agreement to participate, along with an acknowledgment that their rights are protected. The researcher informed participants that the study posed no harm to them. Individual participants were notified that they would not receive any direct benefits from the study.

Results and Discussion

The study's results are presented, examined, and interpreted in this chapter, along with a discussion. The presentation of the findings was founded on the ordered presentation of the study's problem statement and was evaluated and analyzed using the procedures that were determined to be necessary.

Sampling Framework

The study involved 20 participants chosen using a purposive sampling procedure. They were all women leaders holding different designations in Central Mindanao University. They are also selected based on the abovementioned inclusion criteria: having at least five years of leadership experience in higher education. Table 1 represents a summary of the participants' demographic profiles. Code names were given for confidentiality and anonymity purposes.

Table 1. *Participants' Demographic Profile*

<i>Code Name</i>	<i>Leadership Roles</i>	<i>Years of Higher Education Leadership Experience</i>
Participant 1	Chairperson	15
Participant 2	Director	27
Participant 3	Chairperson	28
Participant 4	Chairperson	29
Participant 5	Chairperson	28
Participant 6	Director	27
Participant 7	Dean	24
Participant 8	Director	25
Participant 9	Director	20
Participant 10	Dean	29
Participant 11	Chairperson	20
Participant 12	Dean	28
Participant 13	Chairperson	17
Participant 14	Director	28
Participant 15	Dean	19
Participant 16	Director	20
Participant 17	Dean	18
Participant 18	Director	20
Participant 19	Director	26
Participant 20	Chairperson	29

One-on-one interviews and a focus group discussion were conducted to comprehensively extrapolate the essence of their challenges and triumphs. This was done by identifying common themes and trends from the participants' narratives. The succeeding paragraphs illustrate the gathered answers to the statement of the problems identified in the study.

The flexibility of Leadership Styles in Response to Organizational Culture: Table 2 presents the core theme, sub-themes, and codes of modifying leadership style to suit the university culture or environment. As far as leadership style is concerned, all participants believed that environment and setting are factors that reconfigure how they execute their leadership roles. They argued that they would not necessarily change but rather modify their leadership styles to suit the demands, standards, ideals, and institutional culture and

values of the university in general.

Table 2. *Changing Leadership Style to Succeed in a Particular College/University Culture or Environment*

Core Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
1. Flexibility of Leadership Styles in Response to Organizational Culture	1. Flexibility and Responsiveness	1. Adaptability
	2. Impact of Institutional Culture	2. Influence of Institutional Culture
	3. Embracing Institutional Culture	3. Integration with Institutional Norms
	4. Consistency in Leadership Philosophy	4. Leadership Principle
	5. Empowerment and Mentorship	5. Encouragement and guidance

Participant 1 believes that maintaining flexibility and responsiveness to the unique culture and surroundings of a certain college or university is crucial for leaders. She admitted that she would be willing to modify her leadership style in order to better fit the unique requirements, expectations, and values of the organization, all the while upholding consistency in her basic principles and values. This can entail taking a more cooperative stance in an atmosphere that encourages cooperation and reaching consensus, or it might entail acting more assertively in situations that demand quick decisions. Developing a leadership style that promotes trust, involvement, and effectiveness within the particular setting of the college or university culture is the ultimate objective. Participant 3 illustrated that the culture in the field of research and extension at Central Mindanao University in the 2000s was not that prolific, leaders were not so competitive in these areas. However, the present ideals of CMU in these fields are centered on globalization and internationalization. Hence, leaders also become more research-driven at present, aiming for national and international recognition in the field of research and extension along with instruction and production.

In the same vein, Participant 3 emphasized how flexible the leadership style could be. “There’s no such thing as a permanent leadership style. It depends on what kind of culture is being adopted by the university at the moment,” she said, asserting Participant 7’s contention that leadership is not unilinear but a reciprocal process. If the leader thinks that his/her style is no longer effective and suitable with the current system, then s/he should modify something. “So, we have to be flexible and we have to be open to possible suggestions and comments from seasoned leaders,” Participant 7 added. As Participant 2 puts it:

“The environment and setting strongly impact how we define leadership. Different workplaces and culture shape expectations and what qualities are seen as effective in a leader. Diversity in a college or university culture/environment is inevitable. Since it is inevitable, you must be flexible and adaptable as a leader.”

Moreover, Participant 10 and Participant 4 also pointed out that leaders must be able to blend with the current institutional culture in order to contribute to the mission and vision of the university. “Embrace and embody the culture, adjust your leadership style to meet the demands,” said Participant 10. Participant 4 also shared that she had been through different universities in the past, and she highlighted the importance of blending with distinct educational atmospheres, asserting Participant 5’s take on leadership adaptability.

On the other hand, Participant 9, Participant 12, and Participant 14 amongst others argued that they may modify their leadership styles when necessary but not their general leadership philosophies that molded them as trailblazing leaders in the academic community. Participant 12 believes that her authoritative and transformational leadership are something that all academic contexts need in order to create change and difference. “I’d rather leave a certain university if their values do not fit my leadership ideals. I won’t settle with their weak system even if it takes starting from the bottom all over again. I may adopt something beneficial but my way of leading would stay the same,” she admitted, which is akin to Participant 9’s line, “regardless of what political culture there is, my consultative leadership style would never change.” As Participant 14 put it:

“I don’t think I would change my leadership philosophy because I really believe in flexibility and respect as well as human consideration. Leadership also has something to do with cooperation among your constituents so that you lead by objectives. What the constituents wish to achieve must be considered to see your goals and objectives and strategies. If I will be immersed in a different university culture, I will not change but adapt. I may be flexible, I may retain my leadership styles and adjust with the current environment, but not total change to fit the university.”

For Participant 8, her way of empowering and believing in the capabilities of her team would never be changed as a leader because she believes that leadership is about mentoring his/her subordinates to become effective leaders in the future. “I always believe that they are my team members, and for now, they are my subordinates, but they always have the chance of being my superior also in the future. Do not believe that as a head, you will always be the head. Because leadership here in CMU is designations, and if there’s a change of designation, there will always be another person who will be placed ahead of you. So, you will never have a problem working with whoever is placed in the leadership ring, if while you are ahead of them, you also listen and believe in their power and capability; and knowing that they can also do better than you can,” said Participant 8.

The narratives presented in Table 8 shed light on the adaptability and flexibility of leadership styles in response to the organizational culture and environment within Central Mindanao University (CMU). Participants emphasized the importance of tailoring their leadership approaches to align with the unique requirements, expectations, and values of the institution, while also maintaining consistency with their core principles and values.

One of the key themes that emerged from the narratives is the recognition that leadership styles are not fixed but rather adaptable to

changing circumstances and organizational contexts. Participants acknowledged the dynamic nature of organizational culture and the need for leaders to adjust their styles accordingly. They highlighted the importance of flexibility in leadership, emphasizing the ability to modify approaches based on the prevailing culture and environment.

Participants emphasized the significance of understanding and embodying the culture of the university in order to effectively contribute to its mission and vision. They stressed the importance of blending with the institutional culture while also retaining core leadership philosophies that have guided them as effective leaders in the academic community. This nuanced approach allows leaders to navigate diverse cultural settings while remaining true to their values and principles.

Moreover, participants recognized the reciprocal nature of leadership, emphasizing the importance of openness to feedback and suggestions from seasoned leaders. They highlighted the need for leaders to be adaptable and receptive to changes in the organizational culture, while also maintaining a strong sense of identity and purpose as leaders.

Overall, the narratives underscored the importance of flexibility and adaptability in leadership, as well as the need for leaders to strike a balance between fitting into the organizational culture and staying true to their leadership philosophies. By embracing these principles, leaders can effectively navigate the complexities of the organizational environment and drive positive change within their respective institutions.

Table 3. *Ways on How the Participants' University Supported Their Leadership Development and Career Advancement*

<i>Core Themes</i>	<i>Sub-themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
1. Institutional Support for Leadership Development and Career Advancement	1. Professional Development Opportunities 2. Financial Support and Resources 3. Networking and Collaboration 4. Academic Advancement 5. Impact on Leadership Development	1. Seminars, Training, Conferences, Workshops, 2. Funding for Training and Seminars, Scholarships for Higher Studies 3. Networking Opportunities, Collaboration with Colleagues, National and International Exposure

Institutional Support for Leadership Development and Career Advancement: Table 3 presents the core theme, sub-themes, and leadership development and career advancement support codes. The participants get full support from their institution in several ways. Crucial to their leadership development and career advancement are opportunities like seminars, training, conferences, and workshops that the university permits them to attend. There was also some training particularly devoted to their leadership skills.

Participant 1, chair of the Department of Language Education, shared that they received leadership training programs designed to develop their skills, such as communication, decision-making, and conflict resolution, which empowered their faculty members to take on leadership roles within their department or the university. She also added that these trainings were delivered in partnership with professional development organizations and some external consultants. Participant 1 also mentioned mentorship programs and professional development workshops. She said that experienced faculty members mentor their junior faculty or graduate students, which provides valuable guidance and support for career advancement. In addition, their department organizes workshops and seminars focused on leadership skills, specifically tailored to the needs of educators in language education. They discussed topics like effective classroom management techniques in cultural communication or training technology in language teaching.

Moreover, Participant 6 also ascertained that though their institution is not that wealthy, it always provides their requests for their professional development. "CMU is not selfish. As long as your request is qualified, then they will send you [to pieces of training]. CMU helped me a lot, from my teaching profession to my writing ability and management skills," she said. This is exactly related to Participant 9 who also said that, "Though CMU has no big fund, every time we have projects, they are willing to support us despite limited resources." Majority of the participants would say that their institution hones them to become better leaders in the academic community. As Participant 2 put forward:

"All the achievements in my unit would not be possible without the full support of the administration, in terms of financial and moral support. Sending and allowing me to attend seminars, training, and workshops in other places are truly transformational. We are blessed to have a budget every year to set certain amounts for our training and seminars."

Participant 5 also reported that their national and international exposure to conferences regarding flora and fauna had a tremendous impact on their development as researchers. "CMU would sponsor even international conferences. It has an excellent support system," she claimed. Participant 1, Participant 11, and Participant 14 asserted that these trainings are avenues for networking opportunities, where faculty members can connect with colleagues from other institutions, which can facilitate collaboration, knowledge, exchange, and career advancement. They believe that building a solid professional network can lead to opportunities for research, partnerships, conference presentations, and leadership roles within professional organizations.

On the other hand, the institution also supported the participants in advancing to higher studies like master's or doctoral degrees by granting scholarships. For instance, Participant 14 was given a PhD scholarship twice, PhD for Instructional Systems Design and PhD for Language Studies, which promoted her to a higher academic position earlier, Associate Professor V. Other participants who were allowed to pursue graduate and postgraduate studies are Participant 4, Participant 8, and Participant 9, to mention but a few.

The institution also generously extends financial resources to the participants regarding research and publication. The extension projects of Participant 4 on indigenous language, culture, and arts, for instance, are fully funded by the university. Participant 1 said that providing resources and support for faculty members to engage in research extension and publication activities can enhance their visibility and credibility within the field of language education. This may include access to research funding assistance with manuscript preparation or opportunities for collaboration with colleagues.

The narratives presented in Table 3 highlight the significant support provided by the institution to facilitate leadership development and career advancement among the participants. Central Mindanao University (CMU) demonstrates a solid commitment to the professional growth of its faculty members through various initiatives and resources.

A key aspect of this support is the provision of opportunities for professional development, including seminars, training programs, conferences, and workshops. Participants emphasized the transformative impact of these activities on their skills and competencies, particularly in areas such as communication, decision-making, conflict resolution, and leadership. These programs are often tailored to the specific needs of educators in various fields, ensuring relevance and effectiveness in enhancing their capabilities.

Mentorship programs and workshops organized by the institution further contribute to leadership development by providing guidance and support from experienced faculty members. This mentorship fosters a culture of collaboration and knowledge exchange, empowering junior faculty and graduate students to assume leadership roles within their departments or the university as a whole.

Participants highlighted the institution's willingness to support their professional development initiatives despite financial constraints. CMU demonstrates flexibility and generosity in responding to faculty requests for training and educational opportunities, demonstrating a commitment to investing in the growth and advancement of its academic community.

Furthermore, the institution extends support to faculty members pursuing higher studies, offering scholarships for master's or doctoral degrees. This investment in advanced education not only enhances the expertise and qualifications of individual faculty members but also contributes to the academic prestige and standing of the university.

In addition to professional development opportunities, CMU provides financial resources to support faculty research and publication activities. This funding enables faculty to engage in research projects, extension activities, and scholarly publications, enhancing their visibility and credibility in their respective fields.

Overall, the institutional support described by the participants plays a crucial role in nurturing a culture of continuous learning, growth, and excellence within Central Mindanao University. By investing in its faculty members' professional development and career advancement, CMU strengthens its academic community and contributes to the broader goals of education, research, and service.

Table 4. *Ways on How Mentors and Coaches Assisted the Participants in Developing Their Leadership Skills*

<i>Core Theme</i>	<i>Sub-themes</i>	<i>Codes</i>
1. Mentoring and Coaching for Leadership Development	1. Guidance and Advice 2. Encouragement and Support 3. Feedback and Reflection 4. Setting Goals and Action Plans 5. Skill-building Exercises	1. Insights into Leadership Strategies, Decision-Making Processes, Communication Techniques 2. Reassurance, Motivation, Listening Ear, Confidence Building, Resilience as Leaders 3. Constructive Criticism, Self-Reflection, Introspection, Identifying Strengths and Areas for Improvement

Mentoring and Coaching for Leadership Development: Table 4 presents the core theme, sub-themes, and codes of ways of mentoring and coaching toward leadership skills development. The participants' leadership development was aided by both formal and casual mentoring and coaching by their superior leaders. They consider their higher-ups as their models and at the same time consultants when it comes to certain problems and decision-making. The following are some of the major ways in which mentors and coaches assist the participants:

Guidance and Advice: they offer insights into effective leadership strategies, decision-making processes, and communication techniques, helping the participants develop a deeper understanding of leadership principles. As Participant 14 conveyed, "I was able to imbibe some qualities and characteristics that made me a productive leader through casual sharing of experiences, which formed my leadership skills by applying those I find beneficial and advantageous." As a librarian, Participant 2 asserted that her mentors and coaches had a huge impact on her professional growth as they guided her in developing better organization, responsibility, and communication skills. Their support honed her to become more strategic in managing the library, and in expanding her knowledge in the field. Moreso, even though her superiors are already retired and some are already abroad, Participant 5 said that she can still access them whenever she needs guidance and advice. Additionally, Participant 8 summarized her greatest takeaways from her mentors by saying:

"My mentors taught me that as long as you are calm and you listen to whatever issues, sometimes, you don't even have to give solutions to the clamors of those under you as long as you make them feel that you are with them, you empathize with them, and you know their problems, especially in their offices and the delivery of their functions when there are conflicts, that's already okay. I learned how to

accept things I cannot change. Accept defeat and never ever be afraid to apologize if you made a mistake, and always take responsibility. I also learned that when there is a fallout or mistake committed by your office, it is your command responsibility. When you face the higher office, you should never blame your subordinates. You take it as your own because that is your command responsibility. However, when you are going to meet your subordinates, you have to explain to them that it was their mistake, and correct them for whatever mistakes or failures they have committed. But when facing the higher office, you should never put them in front because you are going to take the bullet for them.”

Participant 1 contended that mentors’ encouragement and invaluable support provide reassurance, motivation, and a listening ear during challenging times, helping administrators build confidence and resilience as leaders.

Feedback and Reflection. They offer constructive feedback on an individual's leadership behaviors, communication, and decision-making processes. They encourage self-reflection and introspection, helping individuals identify their strengths and areas for improvement as leaders. “I faced corrective criticisms from my mentors, and the more I receive them, the more I get challenged to perform better,” said Participant 4. Observing from the way other leaders deliver their function is crucial. Like Participant 10, Participant 7 said that she did not have much formal training on leadership but she learned by merely reflecting from the performance and output of her head. Participant 12 also admitted that she has a go-to person especially when she screwed up with her decision, who trained her in dealing with difficult people in and outside her office.

Setting Goals and Action Plans. Mentors assisted the participants in setting clear and achievable goals for further leadership development. For instance, Participant 3, being the former Chair of the Department of Languages and Literature, was mandated to revise their curriculum to meet the new program offered by their department. She emphasized that her coach was too hands-on in revising their program goals and objectives. “I have a circle of support systems, starting from the VPAA to the Director of Instruction. Different chairpersons also tried to coach each other. I coached one department head and that head also coached somehow. So, there was really an exchange of coaching during my time, and I think that is the kind of culture that administrators and middle admins should have,” she said.

Skill-building Exercises. Senior leaders provided skill-building exercises and activities designed to enhance specific leadership competencies. This includes the formal training and workshops on leadership development and career advancement. For example, Participant 5 mentioned about the “Balik-scientist Program” that their superiors encouraged them to attend to gather insights from scientists who studied abroad. “They offer international linkages as part of the activities we engage in so we can further build our skills in writing biological research.

They also encouraged us to apply for different research funding institutions or attend seminars,” she added. Also, Participant 1 highlighted that their heads facilitate networking opportunities, and help them identify opportunities for leadership development within their organization.

The mentoring and coaching provided by senior leaders play a pivotal role in the leadership development of the participants, as outlined in Table 10. These mentorship relationships, both formal and informal, offer a range of benefits that contribute to the growth and effectiveness of the participants as leaders.

Guidance and advice form the cornerstone of mentorship, with mentors offering insights into effective leadership strategies, decision-making processes, and communication techniques. By sharing their experiences and expertise, mentors empower the participants to develop a deeper understanding of leadership principles and cultivate essential skills for success in their roles. Moreover, mentors serve as role models, demonstrating leadership qualities and behaviors that inspire and guide the participants in their own leadership journey.

Feedback and reflection are also integral components of the mentorship process, providing participants with constructive criticism and opportunities for self-improvement. Mentors offer valuable feedback on leadership behaviors, communication styles, and decision-making processes, helping participants identify their strengths and areas for growth. This feedback encourages self-reflection and introspection, fostering a continuous learning and development cycle.

Setting goals and action plans is another key aspect of mentorship. Mentors assist participants in defining clear and achievable objectives for their leadership development. By collaboratively setting goals and action plans, mentors help participants chart a course for their professional growth and advancement. Mentors also provide guidance and support as participants work towards achieving their goals, offering encouragement and accountability along the way.

Skill-building exercises complement formal mentorship activities, providing participants opportunities to enhance specific leadership competencies. Mentors may facilitate workshops, training programs, or other skill-building activities to develop essential leadership skills and abilities. These exercises help participants acquire new knowledge, build confidence, and expand their leadership capabilities.

Overall, the mentoring and coaching provided by senior leaders offer invaluable support and guidance to the participants as they navigate their leadership roles. Mentors empower participants by offering guidance and advice, providing feedback and reflection, setting goals and action plans, and facilitating skill-building exercises to realize their full leadership potential and make meaningful contributions to their organizations.

Table 5. *Experiences Influencing the Participants' Development and their Advice to Aspiring Women Leaders*

Core Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
1. Leadership Development through Experiences and Advice	1. Learning from Different Leadership Experiences 2. Navigating Leadership Roles 3. People Management Skills 4. Believing in Oneself 5. Seeking Mentorship 6. Advocating for Oneself 7. Supporting Other Women 8. Staying Resilient 9. Leading with Empathy 10. Aiming for Advancement 11. Learning from Experienced Leaders	1. Exposure to Various Leadership Styles 2. Flexibility, Productivity, Innovation, Transformation 3. Managing Diverse Personalities, Techniques and Strategies, Proper Supervision and Management 4. Confidence, Trusting Instincts, Recognizing Strengths, Embracing Unique Perspective 5. Guidance, Feedback, Learning from Experiences, 6. Assertiveness, Negotiation Skills, Self-Advocacy 7. Empowerment, Collaboration, Creating Networks 8. Active Listening, Understanding Diverse Perspectives 9. Lifelong Learning, Professional Development, Pursuing Higher Education

Leadership Development through Experiences and Advice: Table 5 presents the core theme, sub-themes, and codes of experiences influencing their development. Different leadership experiences have hugely contributed to the development of the participants. These experiences were instrumental in navigating the complexities of their leadership roles. Being exposed to different kinds of leaders served as an opportunity for Participant 8 and Participant 9 to learn significant leadership strategies. As Participant 8 put it:

“As a leader, you will be multitasking and exposed to different groups, leaders, and committees. Sometimes, that seems too taxing but that is a very good experience because that’s where you get to meet brilliant and those who are not too brilliant leaders. You get to compare them, and you know which ones to take on. It seems like you have a free benchmarking experience, and when you listen to your leaders, you would say I would never do what she did because this is how I feel, and I know that this is how my other members in the future would feel. But what she did was brilliant, and I will do it that way.”

Having worked at CMU for 27 years, Participant 9 encountered various leaders who became her model in delivering her leadership functions. She stated that she experienced many presidents, and they were eye-openers on the different ways of leading the university. “It was a great experience to see how you would take on your leadership role. The experience is the best teacher. You would probably cry immediately if the higher-ups scolded you. But you will learn many things by reflecting on seasoned leaders you are working with,” she added.

Further, their leadership roles prompted the participants to be flexible and productive. Participant 10 admitted that she had some critical experiences when she became the Dean of the College of Education, which drove her to become an innovative and transformational leader. The same holds for Participant 12, who reported that she was able to develop a bold character when she was concurrently appointed as the Director of the Office of Admissions, Scholarships, and Placement and Director of the CMU-Laboratory High School. Thus, difficult situations in their respective offices propelled them to incorporate efficient decision-making and problem-solving abilities, which also deliberately equipped them to become trailblazing academic leaders. As Participant 12 put it:

“The greatest impact on my development is those moments when I find it extremely difficult to decide, especially when some parties vehemently oppose my plans. Crossroad situations like that make you feel trapped. There are some times when our greatest enemy as leaders is ourselves.”

For Participant 1, leaders should take advantage of challenging opportunities. They must embrace difficult situations that push them outside their comfort zone, whether leading a project, presenting at a conference, or taking on a new role. These experiences provide valuable learning opportunities and help leaders develop confidence.

On the other hand, people management is another salient factor that catapulted their development as leaders. Participant 3 ascertained that it took her a while to develop techniques and strategies to manage people because people in a particular unit have diverse personalities. “To manage people is difficult, and it will take time,” she said. Participant 9 and Participant 11 also asserted that it is immensely crucial to guide people in achieving their office's objectives, which need proper supervision and management. Organizations whose leaders cannot manage their workforce effectively will lead to fallouts and conflicts between members.

Advice to Aspiring Women Leaders

The participants set forth empowering and transformational advice for aspiring women leaders to ponder for their leadership journey. The following are vital qualities women leaders should inculcate as they execute their leadership roles not just in the academic community but in all forms of organization:

They believe in themselves. Women leaders should have confidence in their abilities and trust their instincts as leaders. They should recognize their strength, embrace their unique perspective, and believe they can make a meaningful impact. For Participant 13, this encompasses accepting whatever roles and challenges are entrusted to them. Women leaders should accept offers as they are great

professional empowerment and development avenues. According to Participant 6, trust and confidence in oneself are indispensable in executing leadership functions. One can only be influential if one has faith in one's abilities. Participant 14 also said that women leaders must embody their leadership philosophies and never be afraid to voice out their ideas and visions for the betterment of the organization. "Be authentic to yourself as a leader. Embrace your unique strengths, perspectives, and leadership style, and have confidence in your abilities to lead and make a difference," said Participant 1.

Seek Mentorship. Women leaders should surround themselves with mentors, sponsors, and supportive colleagues who can offer guidance, advice, and encouragement. "They should learn from their experiences, seek feedback, and leverage their networks to advance their careers," said Participant 1. Mentorship can offer guidance, support, and opportunities for growth and serve as a source of inspiration.

Advocate for Oneself. Women leaders should advocate for their advancement and speak up for what they deserve. They should be bold in negotiating opportunities, promotions, or compensation that reflect their value and contributions. "Aspiring women leaders should be able to express themselves. Learn to be bold and distinguish your wants and needs in a unit, and don't be afraid," said Participant 3.

Support Other Women. They should lift other women leaders as they climb by supporting and empowering them in their leadership journeys. They should create networks, mentorship programs, and spaces for collaboration where women can thrive and support one another. According to Participant 15, women should have the same opportunities for development in their careers and leadership. They should have full support, understanding, and consideration for their maternal and domestic responsibilities while pursuing their career advancement and delivering their leadership functions.

Stay Resilient. Leadership can be challenging, and setbacks are inevitable. Women leaders should develop resilience and perseverance to overcome obstacles and fallouts in their offices. They should stay focused on their goals, maintain a positive mindset, and learn from setbacks as opportunities for growth. Participant 1 says, "Resilience and perseverance are vital in facing challenges and setbacks. Leadership can be challenging and demanding, but by staying resilient, you can overcome obstacles and continue to thrive." Participant 15 also emphasized that part of being resilient is "not taking negative criticisms personally" because they are inevitable for all leaders. "You will never triumph without challenges like negative remarks against your leadership. Being a woman leader combines challenges and triumphs; they go together," said Participant 4.

Lead with Empathy. They should lead with empathy, compassion, and inclusivity. They should listen actively, understand diverse perspectives, and foster a culture of belonging where everyone feels valued and heard. Participant 6 admitted that many women leaders are temperamental, easily affected by mood swings and short-temperedness. "Women leaders should control their emotions. Even if they are so good at performing their functions, if they don't control their emotions, they will destroy their selves," she said. This goes hand in hand with Participant 11's narrative that women leaders should have patience and character that is willing to listen to others and willing to change.

Aim for Advancement. Women leaders should aim to acquire new skills and a higher level of competence in their expertise, which is crucial for expanding their career growth and more leadership opportunities. As Participant 1 put it: "Women leaders should commit to continuous lifelong learning and professional development. You should stay abreast of current trends, research, and best practices in your field and seek opportunities to expand your knowledge and skills through workshops, courses, and conferences." Participant 5 also emphasized that they should pursue higher education, such as master's and Ph.D. degrees, to open doors of opportunities like higher positions in the academic context.

Learn from the Experienced Leaders. Women leaders can gain valuable insights from great leaders around them. They may reflect on others' leadership styles, successes, ways of resolving hurdles, and most importantly, their mistakes and how they deal with them. As Participant 14 conveyed it:

"I became a leader because I followed some leaders earlier in my career. I look up to somebody and their qualities that are worth emulating. By just looking at the role models in the department, I could pick roles that I thought were best for me and reject those that may affect my leadership style. It is a matter of picking up and rejecting what is not good."

She also emphasizes that women leaders should listen to their heads and learn from their leadership philosophies, adaptability, flexibility, and, most importantly, strategies for achieving the organization's mission and vision. Participant 12 also agreed with Participant 14 by saying, "Women leaders who had just begun their leadership journey should look for someone they can look up to and be willing to embrace change for themselves."

As highlighted in Table 11, the participants' experiences have significantly shaped their leadership development. Through various leadership roles and encounters with different leaders, the participants have gained valuable insights, skills, and perspectives that have influenced their growth and effectiveness in their respective positions.

Exposure to diverse leadership styles and approaches has been instrumental in the participants' development. By observing and interacting with different leaders, they have learned from both positive and negative examples, refining their leadership strategies and behaviors. This exposure has provided them with a wealth of knowledge and perspectives to draw upon as they navigate the complexities of their leadership roles.

Challenging experiences have also been pivotal in the participants' development as leaders. Confronting difficult situations, making tough decisions, and overcoming obstacles have helped them build resilience, confidence, and problem-solving abilities. These experiences have pushed them outside their comfort zones and encouraged them to develop innovative and adaptive approaches to leadership.

Furthermore, the participants have emphasized the importance of influential people management in their leadership development. Learning to navigate diverse personalities, manage conflicts, and inspire and motivate others has been essential for their success as leaders. Through trial and error, they have honed their skills in managing teams and fostering collaboration, which has been crucial for achieving their organizational objectives.

In addition to their own experiences, the participants have benefited from the advice and guidance of mentors and coaches. These mentors have provided valuable insights, feedback, and support, helping the participants navigate their leadership roles with confidence and clarity. By leveraging the wisdom and expertise of these mentors, the participants have accelerated their growth and development as leaders.

Overall, the participants' experiences have been transformative in their leadership journeys. By embracing challenges, learning from diverse leadership styles, and seeking guidance from mentors, they have developed the skills, resilience, and confidence needed to excel in their leadership roles. Their insights and advice offer valuable lessons for aspiring women leaders as they embark on their leadership journeys.

Conclusions

Participants characterized the culture and norms of contemporary academic institutions as influential factors shaping opportunities for advancement among women in advanced leadership positions. They highlighted the importance of institutional culture, values, and environment in shaping leadership styles and behaviors. Flexibility and adaptability were emphasized as essential qualities for women leaders to navigate diverse institutional cultures and effectively lead within different contexts. Furthermore, the study revealed the significance of institutional support and resources in creating an enabling environment for women's career advancement. Policies promoting gender diversity, mentorship programs, and opportunities for leadership development were identified as critical components of supportive institutional cultures that facilitate women's advancement in higher education. These findings underscore the importance of fostering inclusive and supportive institutional environments that recognize and value the contributions of women leaders. By addressing systemic barriers and promoting gender equity within academic institutions, opportunities for advancement can be enhanced, leading to greater diversity and representation in higher education leadership positions.

Thus, the research on women leaders within Central Mindanao University (CMU) revealed a complex interplay of factors shaping their career paths and current positions. Educational attainment, including doctoral degrees and academic distinctions, emerged as instrumental in propelling women into leadership roles, alongside a genuine passion for service and community development. However, biases and stereotypes, compounded by campus politics, hinder women's career advancement, perpetuating gender disparities in leadership positions. Environmental factors, such as organizational culture and academic norms, influence leadership behaviors and necessitate adaptive strategies. Institutional support systems, including leadership development programs and mentorship techniques, foster effective leadership.

Moreover, diverse experiences, resilience, and people management skills contributed to leadership development among women leaders at CMU. Looking ahead, addressing biases, promoting equitable opportunities, and fostering supportive environments are essential for advancing gender equality and promoting inclusive leadership practices within higher education institutions. The participants' advice for aspiring women leaders underscored the importance of self-belief, mentorship, resilience, and continuous learning, emphasizing the need for authenticity and adaptability in navigating the complexities of leadership. Ultimately, the leadership journey of women within CMU reflects a commitment to service, resilience, and a dedication to excellence in higher education, pointing towards a future of increased gender diversity and inclusive leadership practices within academia.

Further examination of the research findings illuminates the nuanced dynamics influencing women's leadership trajectories within Central Mindanao University (CMU). While educational qualifications and a passion for service are foundational elements, the prevalence of biases and stereotypes underscores broader societal challenges that impede women's career advancement. These biases, often reinforced by campus politics, not only limit access to opportunities but also shape perceptions of women's leadership capabilities, perpetuating gender disparities within the institution. Moreover, the interplay of gender with other identities, such as race, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status, adds layers of complexity to women's experiences in leadership roles, highlighting the importance of adopting an intersectional lens in addressing inequality.

The role of institutional culture emerges as a critical factor influencing women's leadership experiences, with leaders navigating and adapting to evolving cultural norms and expectations. The need for flexibility and adaptability in leadership styles is evident as leaders strive to balance their principles with the demands of the organizational context. Moreover, institutional support mechanisms, including mentorship programs and professional growth opportunities, play a crucial role in empowering women leaders and mitigating the impact of systemic barriers. However, the effectiveness of these support systems may vary, underscoring the importance of tailored

approaches that address the particular needs and challenges women face in leadership positions.

The experiences and insights shared by participants underscore the complexity of women's leadership journeys and offer valuable lessons for aspiring leaders. The emphasis on self-belief, resilience, and continuous learning reflects a recognition of the inherent challenges women face in leadership roles and a commitment to overcoming obstacles and driving positive change. Moreover, the call for women to support and empower each other highlights the importance of solidarity and collective action in advancing gender equality within academic institutions.

Looking ahead, the research calls for a multifaceted approach to promoting gender diversity and inclusive leadership practices within CMU and similar institutions. This approach should encompass targeted efforts to address biases and stereotypes, create supportive institutional cultures, and provide robust support systems for women leaders. Moreover, it underscores the importance of fostering a diverse talent pipeline and providing opportunities for leadership development at all career stages. By embracing these principles and practices, CMU can position itself as a leader in advocating gender equality and inclusive leadership within the higher education landscape.

Based on the challenges identified in the study regarding trailblazing women in higher education, several recommendations may be considered to address these issues effectively, benefiting not only Central Mindanao University (CMU) but also the Commission on Higher Education, women, future researchers, and higher education institutions at large:

Comprehensive Gender Diversity Initiatives. It is suggested that the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) collaborates with universities, including CMU, to implement comprehensive gender diversity initiatives. These initiatives should promote equitable opportunities for women in leadership across all higher education institutions. Setting targets for the representation of women in senior positions and implementing policies to mitigate biases and stereotypes can contribute to women's career advancement in academia.

Training and Awareness Programs. CHED and universities can organize regular training sessions and awareness projects to educate faculty, staff, and students about gender biases and stereotypes. These programs can create a more inclusive campus environment where women feel supported and empowered to pursue leadership positions. Such initiatives can benefit women, future researchers, and all academic community members.

Mentorship and Sponsorship Programs. Universities and CHED can build formal mentorship and sponsorship programs to provide women leaders with guidance, support, and networking opportunities. Pairing aspiring women leaders with experienced mentors can help them explore the complexities of higher education leadership. Additionally, CHED can encourage universities to allocate resources for mentorship and sponsorship programs to support women's career development.

Flexible Work Policies. CHED can advocate for implementing flexible work policies across higher education institutions. These policies should accommodate the diverse needs of women leaders, including parental leave, flexible scheduling, and remote work options. Providing support for work-life balance can help retain talented women in leadership positions and contribute to a more inclusive academic environment.

Leadership Development Opportunities. CHED may collaborate with universities to invest in leadership development opportunities tailored specifically for women leaders. This can include funding training programs, workshops, and conferences to enhance leadership skills and competencies. By providing opportunities for professional growth, CHED can empower women leaders to thrive in higher education.

Promotion of Inclusive Leadership Practices. CHED and universities should work together to foster a culture of inclusive leadership that values diverse perspectives, fosters collaboration, and promotes empathy and respect among faculty, staff, and students. Leaders should lead by example and commit to creating a supportive and inclusive work environment.

Advocacy and Policy Change. CHED can advocate for policy changes at the national level to address systemic barriers to women's career advancement in higher education. This may include revising national promotion and tenure criteria policies and implementing transparent and equitable hiring and promotion processes across all higher education institutions.

Research and Data Collection. CHED can support research initiatives and data collection efforts focused on the experiences and challenges conquered by women in higher education leadership roles. By funding research projects and collecting data on gender equity in academia, CHED can inform evidence-based interventions and policies to promote gender diversity and inclusion within the higher education sector.

To address biases and stereotypes against women leaders in higher education, CHED and the research community may implement measures such as awareness campaigns, diversity training programs, and the promotion of inclusive leadership practices within academic institutions.

By diversifying efforts across multiple stakeholders, including CHED, women, future researchers, and higher education institutions, proactive solutions can address the challenges faced by trailblazing women in higher education and create an inclusive and equitable academic atmosphere.

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